

An Expression A Day

AEAD PDF Book

No. 401-500 / 99 entries

Hilofumi Yamamoto, Ph.D.

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No doubt about it

まちが
間違いはない

Machigai nai

No doubt about it

Variants

- まちが間違いはない

No doubt about it

- まちが間違いはないって

I'm telling you

- まちが間違いはないよ

I'm sure of it

- まちが間違いはないから

Definitely

- ぜったい絶対、そうだよ

I'm certain

Adjusted Expression

A 「あした明日はは晴れるでしょうか」 B 「はい、は晴れるかのうせい可能性がたか高いとおも思います」

A: Do you think it will be sunny tomorrow? B: Yes, I think it is very likely to be sunny.

Example

A 「あした明日はは晴れるかな？」 B 「まちが間違いはないよ」

A: Do you think it will be sunny tomorrow? B: No doubt about it.

Notes

"Machigai nai" expresses strong confidence in the moment. It can be used not only for facts that are certain, but also for things that cannot be fully guaranteed, such as the weather. In this example, it gives a firm answer to A's uncertain question.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

certainty

assertion

emphasis

reassurance

seeking agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

certainty expression

assertion expression

emphasis expression

sharing reassurance

seeking agreement

spoken language

I have to eat

た
食べなくちゃ

Tabenakucha

I have to eat

Variants

- た
食べなくちゃ

I have to eat

- た
食べなきゃ

I need to eat

- た
食べないと

I gotta eat

- た
食べなきゃいけない

I should eat

- た
食べなければなりません

I must eat

Adjusted Expression

A 「そろそろしょくじ食事をしなければなりません」 B 「そうですね。食べたほうがいいですね」

A: I should eat soon. B: Yes, you should eat.

Example

A 「もう12時じだ。食べなくちゃ」 B 「うん、食べたなきゃ」

A: It's already twelve. I have to eat. B: Yeah, you should.

Notes

"Tabenakucha" is a casual shortened form of "tabenakereba ikenai," meaning "I have to eat." In this example, the speaker notices the time and prompts themselves to act. Rather than a formal obligation, it works as a short self-prompt that moves the speaker toward the next action.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

necessity obligation self-prompting starting an action

Tags EN

immediate grammar necessity expression obligation expression self-prompting

ellipsis contracted expression spoken language

Just as I thought

やっぱり

Yappari

Just as I thought

Variants

- やっぱり
Just as I thought
- やっば
As expected
- やっばね
I knew it
- やっばさ
After all
- やはり
Sure enough

Adjusted Expression

A 「あした明日はは晴れるでしょうか」 B 「はやはり、おも晴れないと思います」

A: Do you think it will be sunny tomorrow? B: As I expected, I do not think it will be sunny.

Example

A 「あした明日はは晴れるかな？」 B 「はやっぱり晴れないよ」

A: Do you think it will be sunny tomorrow? B: Just as I thought, it won't be sunny.

Notes

"Yappari" is used when something confirms what the speaker had already thought or expected. In this example, B had expected that it would not be sunny and says "yappari harenai yo." It is not just agreement, but a reaction of reconfirmation: "just as I thought."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reconfirmation confirming an expectation certainty realization agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar reconfirmation expression confirming an expectation
certainty expression realization expression reaction expression spoken language

Maybe I can

できるかも

Dekiru kamo

Maybe I can

Variants

- できるかも
Maybe I can
- できるかもしれない
I might be able to
- できるかもね
I might manage
- できるかもよ
I guess I could
- なんとかできるかも
Maybe I can make it

Adjusted Expression

A 「この問題は、これだけヒントがあれば解けそうではありませんか」 B 「そうですね。もしかしたら、できるかもしれません」

A: With this many hints, this problem seems solvable, doesn't it? B: Yes.
Maybe I can do it.

Example

A 「この問題^{もんだい}、これだけヒント^{ひんと}があれば、簡単^{かんたん}じゃない？」 B 「うん、できるかも」

A: With this many hints, this problem should be easy, right? B: Yeah, maybe I can do it.

Notes

"Dekiru kamo" expresses a possibility without full confidence. In this example, A points out that there are enough hints, and B responds "dekiru kamo," becoming a little more positive. It is not a firm claim, but a real-time expression of a possibility that has just become visible.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

possibility

tentative judgment

hope

self-assessment

softening

Tags EN

immediate grammar

possibility expression

guessing expression

tentative expression

self-assessment

ongoing judgment

spoken language

But it's delicious

おいしいのに...

Oishii noni...

But it's delicious...

Variants

- おいしいのに
But it's delicious...
- おいしいのになあ
Even though it's delicious...
- おいしいのにね
It's so good, though...
- おいしかったのに
But it was delicious...
- こんなにおいしいのに
Even though it's this good...

Adjusted Expression

A 「^{なっとう}納豆はあまり^す好きではありません」 B 「そうですか。おいしいと^{おも}思うのですが、好きではないのですね」

A: I don't really like natto. B: I see. I think it is delicious, but you don't like it.

Example

A 「^{なっとう}納豆、きれい」 B 「え、おいしいのに...」

A: I don't like natto. B: Huh? But it's delicious...

Notes

"Oishii noni" is used when the other person's reaction or the situation does not match the speaker's own feeling. In this example, A says they do not like natto, and B responds with "oishii noni..." in a disappointed way. By stopping at "noni," the speaker leaves feelings such as "Why don't you like it?" or "What a waste" unstated.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

regret

disagreement

emotional mismatch

seeking shared feeling

seeking agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adversative expression

regret expression

reaction expression

emotional expression

unfinished utterance

spoken language

What should we do?

どうする？

Dousuru?

What should we do?

Variants

- どうする？
What should we do?
- どうしよう？
What should I do?
- どうするの？
What are we going to do?
- どうしようかな？
What do we do now?
- これ、どうする？
What should we do about this?

Adjusted Expression

A 「あした明日はあめ雨がふ降るそうですが、どうしまししょううか」 B 「あめ雨でも、い行くひつよう必要があります」

A: I heard it will rain tomorrow. What should we do? B: Even if it rains, we need to go.

Example

A 「あした明日、あめ雨だって。どうする？」 B 「あめ雨でも、い行かなくちゃ」

A: They say it's going to rain tomorrow. What should we do? B: Even if it rains, we have to go.

Notes

"Dousuru?" is used when the speaker asks what action should be taken next. In this example, A hears that it will rain and asks B whether they should change their plan. It can be used for one's own hesitation or for a decision shared with someone else.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

consultation choice asking for a decision hesitation deciding an action

Tags EN

immediate grammar consultation expression choice expression asking for a decision
hesitation deciding an action spoken language

I accidentally...

うっかり

Ukkari

I accidentally...

Variants

- うっかり
I accidentally...
- うっかりして
by mistake
- うっかりしてた
without thinking
- うっかりしっちゃった
I forgot
- つい、うっかり
I wasn't paying attention

Adjusted Expression

A 「^{ちゅうい}注意が^た足りず、^{かさ}傘を^{わす}忘れてしまいました」 B 「^{こま}そうですか。それは^{こま}困りましたね」

A: I was not careful enough and forgot my umbrella. B: I see. That must be inconvenient.

Example

A 「うっかりして、^{かさ}傘、^{わす}忘れちゃった」 B 「それ、^{やすもの}安物でしょ？」

A: I accidentally forgot my umbrella. B: It was a cheap one, right?

Notes

"Ukkari" is used when something happens unintentionally because the speaker was not paying enough attention. In this example, A explains forgetting the umbrella with "ukkari shite." It is not a serious apology, but a quick way to express a small regret or excuse in the moment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

mistake

lack of attention

light regret

excuse

unintentionality

Tags EN

immediate grammar

mistake expression

lack of attention

light regret

unintentionality

excuse expression

spoken language

I ended up...

つい、...してしまった

Tsui ... shite shimatta

I ended up...

Variants

- つい、...してしまった
I ended up...
- つい、...しちゃった
I accidentally...
- つい、...しちゃいました
I couldn't help...
- つい、...してしまいました
I did it without meaning to
- ついつい、...してしまった
Before I knew it, I...

Adjusted Expression

A 「おいしかったので、^{おも}思わず、たくさん^た食べてしまいました」

A: It was delicious, so I ended up eating a lot.

Example

A 「おいしいんで、つい、いっぱい^た食べちゃった」

A: It was so delicious, I ended up eating a lot.

Notes

"Tsui ... shite shimatta" is used when the speaker is carried by the situation or feeling and ends up doing something. In this example, the food was so good that the speaker ate more than planned. It is not a serious mistake, but it carries a light regret or excuse: "I didn't really mean to, but..."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

mistake

light regret

impulse

unintentionality

excuse

Tags EN

immediate grammar

mistake expression

light regret

impulse

unintentionality

excuse expression

spoken language

So good!

うま！

Uma!

So good!

Variants

- うま！
So good!
- うまい！
Delicious!
- うっま！
Tasty!
- うまいよ！
Yum!
- めっちゃうま！
This is really good!

Adjusted Expression

A 「^た食べてみてください」 B 「とてもおいしいです」

A: Please try it. B: It is very delicious.

Example

A 「^た食べてみて」 B 「うま！」

A: Try it. B: So good!

Notes

"Uma!" is a casual, reflexive reaction used when something tastes good. It is a shortened form of "umai," with the final "i" dropped, so the evaluation comes out quickly before any explanation. It sounds natural in close or casual situations, but "oishii desu" is safer in polite settings.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation emotional expression joy surprise reflexive reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar evaluation expression emotional expression reflexive reaction
shortened expression casual expression spoken language

What are you doing?

なに
何なにやってんの？

Nani yatten no?

What are you doing?

Variants

- なに何なにやってんの？

What are you doing?

- なに何なにやってるの？

What are you up to?

- なに何なにしてんの？

What are you working on?

- なに何なにしてるの？

What are you doing there?

- なに何なにやってるわけ？

What do you think you're doing?

Adjusted Expression

A 「いま今、なに何なにをしているのですか」 B 「べんきょう勉強べんきょうしています」

A: What are you doing now? B: I am studying.

Example

A 「なに何なにやってんの？」 B 「べんきょう勉強べんきょうしてるよ」

A: What are you doing? B: I'm studying.

Notes

"Nani yatten no?" is a casual way to ask what someone is doing. It is a contracted form of "nani yatteru no?" and sounds natural in close or informal situations. Depending on tone, however, it can sound not only curious but also surprised or mildly critical, like "What do you think you're doing?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

question

interest

confirmation

surprise

mild criticism

Tags EN

immediate grammar

question expression

confirmation expression

interest expression

surprise

contracted expression

spoken language

I caught a cold

かぜ
風邪ひいた

Kaze hiita

I caught a cold

Variants

- 風邪ひいた

I caught a cold

- 風邪ひいちゃった

I got a cold

- 風邪ひいちゃいました

I ended up catching a cold

- 風邪をひいてしまった

I seem to have caught a cold

- 風邪っぽい

I feel like I'm coming down with something

Adjusted Expression

A 「風邪をひいてしまいました」 B 「大丈夫ですか。薬は飲みましたか」

A: I have caught a cold. B: Are you okay? Did you take any medicine?

Example

A 「風邪ひいた」 B 「大丈夫？薬飲んだ？」

A: I caught a cold. B: Are you okay? Did you take any medicine?

Notes

"Kaze hiita" is a short casual way to say that the speaker has caught a cold. It comes from "kaze o hiita," with the particle "o" omitted. In this example, A reports the condition briefly, and B responds with concern.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reporting one's condition

illness

minor trouble

sharing concern

self-explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

health report

illness expression

minor trouble

ellipsis

inviting a response

spoken language

And on top of that

でもって

Demotte

And on top of that

Variants

- でもって
And on top of that
- それでもって
And then
- それで
So then
- しかも
Plus
- そのうえ
What's more

Adjusted Expression

きのう あめ ふ 昨日は雨が降っていました。さらに、かぜ つよ 風も強かったです。

It was raining yesterday. In addition, the wind was strong.

Example

きのう あめ 昨日は雨だった、でもってかぜ つよ 風も強かった。

Yesterday it rained, and on top of that, the wind was strong too.

Notes

"Demotte" is a casual connector used to add more information to what has just been said. In this example, the speaker adds that the wind was strong after saying that it rained. It feels less like a carefully organized explanation and more like adding information as the story moves along.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

connection

addition

linking

supplementing

momentum

Tags EN

immediate grammar

connecting expression

addition expression

linking speech

supplementing

casual expression

spoken language

In the end

なんだかんだで

Nandakanda de

In the end

Variants

- なんだかんだで
In the end
- なんだかんだ^い言って
After all
- なんだかんだの^{すえ}末に
When all is said and done
- ^{けっきょく}結局
After everything
- いろいろあったけど
One way or another

Adjusted Expression

いろいろなことがありましたが、^{さいしゅうてき}最終的には^{かれ}彼が^か勝つ^{おも}と思います。

Various things may happen, but in the end, I think he will win.

Example

なんだかんだで^{かれ}彼が^か勝つんだよね。

In the end, he wins, you know.

Notes

"Nandakanda de" is a casual expression used to summarize various details or complications and move to the final result. In this example, the speaker suggests that, despite everything that may happen, he will win in the end.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

conclusion

summary

compressing the process

light acceptance

presenting the result

Tags EN

immediate grammar

summary expression

conclusion expression

compressing the process

presenting the result

casual expression

spoken language

Something about...

どうのこうの

Dou no kou no

something about...

Variants

- どうのこうの
something about...
- どうこう
this and that
- ああだこうだ
such and such
- あれこれ
blah blah
- ^{なに}何やかや
one thing or another

Adjusted Expression

詳しいことは覚えていませんが、税金ぜいきんに関する話はなしだったと思います。おも

I do not remember the details, but I think it was something about taxes.

Example

よくわからないけど、税金ぜいきんがどうのこうのという話はなしだったかな？

I'm not really sure, but I think it was something about taxes.

Notes

"Dou no kou no" is used when the speaker does not state the details clearly and only gives a vague idea of the topic. In this example, the speaker does not remember the details, but says it was something about taxes. It can also be used to brush over complaints or criticism.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

skipping details

glossing over circumstances

vague memory

light complaint

summary

Tags EN

immediate grammar

vague expression

skipping details

glossing over circumstances

summary expression

repetition

spoken language

Nothing at all

さっぱり

Sappari

Nothing at all

Variants

- さっぱり
Nothing at all
- さっぱりわからない
Not at all
- さっぱりできない
I don't understand at all
- さっぱりだめ
It isn't going well at all
- さっぱりしない
No progress at all

Adjusted Expression

A 「今日の^{きょう}成果^{せい}はどうでしたか」 B 「まったくうまくいきませんでした」

A: How were today's results? B: It did not go well at all.

Example

A 「今日の^{きょう}成果^{せい}は？」 B 「さっぱり」

A: How were today's results? B: Nothing at all.

Notes

"Sappari" is used when the speaker gets no expected result or understanding at all. In this example, B answers only "sappari" to the question about today's results. With one short word, B conveys that things did not go well or that there was no progress.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

negation

no result

dissatisfaction

confusion

light resignation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

negative expression

no result

dissatisfaction expression

confusion

ellipsis

spoken language

That's good in its own way

それはそれで...いいんじゃない？

Sore wa sore de... iin janai?

That's good in its own way, isn't it?

Variants

- それはそれでいいんじゃない？
That's good in its own way, isn't it?
- それはそれでアリじゃない？
That's acceptable, right?
- まあ、それはそれでいいか
Well, that's okay, I guess.
- それはそれで味^{あじ}があるね
It has its own charm.
- それはそれで悪^{わる}くないね
That's not bad in its own way.

Adjusted Expression

A 「失敗^{しっぱい}作^{さく}のケーキ^{けーき}は、見た目^{みめ}がかなり崩^{くず}れています」 B 「しかし、それはそ
れで手作^{てづく}りらしさがあってよいと思^{おも}います」

A: This failed cake looks quite messy. B: However, I think it has a handmade charm in its own way.

Example

A 「失敗作しっぱいさくのケーキけーき、見た目みめはぐちゃぐちゃだよ」 B 「でも、それはそれで、手作り感てづくかんあっていいんじゃない？」

A: This failed cake looks like a total mess. B: But that's good in its own way. It has a handmade charm, doesn't it?

Notes

"Sore wa sore de" is used to reframe something that might normally seem negative. In this example, B reframes a messy-looking cake as having a handmade charm. It does not deny the failure completely, but gives it another kind of value in the moment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

acceptance

rephrasing

positive reframing

comforting

softening

Tags EN

immediate grammar

acceptance expression

positive reframing

comforting expression

softening expression

evaluation expression

spoken language

Nonstop

ひっきりなしに

Hikkiri nashi ni

nonstop

Variants

- ひっきりなしに
nonstop
- ひっきりなしで
without pause
- ひっきりなしだ
constantly
- ^た絶^まえ間なく
incessantly
- ^{つぎ}次^{つぎ}から次へと
one after another

Adjusted Expression

^{らいきやく}来客が^た絶^まえ間なくあり、^{やす}休^{じかん}む時間がありませんでした。

Visitors came continuously, and there was no time to rest.

Example

ひっきりなしに^{らいきやく}来客があつて、^{やす}休^{ひま}む暇がない。

Visitors keep coming nonstop, leaving no time to rest.

Notes

"Hikkiri nashi ni" describes something continuing without a break. In this example, visitors keep coming one after another, leaving no time to rest. It suggests not only high frequency, but also a continuous flow that can feel tiring or overwhelming.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

continuity

uninterruptedness

busyness

situation description

being overwhelmed

Tags EN

immediate grammar

situation description

continuity expression

frequency expression

busyness expression

being overwhelmed

spoken language

Over and over

く かえ く かえ
繰り返し繰り返し

Kurikaeshi kurikaeshi

over and over

Variants

- く かえ く かえ
• 繰り返し繰り返し

over and over

- く かえ
• 繰り返し

repeatedly

- なんど なんど
• 何度も何度も

again and again

- なんど
• 何度も

time and again

- なんかい
• 何回も

many times

Adjusted Expression

なんど く かえ りかい
何度も繰り返して、やっと理解できました。

After repeating it many times, I finally understood.

Example

A 「同じことを繰り返し繰り返し言ってるね」 B 「うん、何度も言うのが大事なんだよ」

A: You keep saying the same thing over and over. B: Yeah, saying it many times is important.

Notes

"Kurikaeshi kurikaeshi" emphasizes doing the same thing many times. A single "kurikaeshi" already means repetition, but repeating the word adds a stronger sense of persistence or repeated effort. In this example, it shows the importance of saying the same thing many times.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

repetition

emphasis

continuity

internalization

persistence

Tags EN

immediate grammar

repetition expression

emphasis expression

situation description

continuity expression

learning expression

spoken language

Let's get started

さあ、^{はじ}始めよう

Saa, hajimeyou

Alright, let's get started

Variants

- さあ、^{はじ}始めよう
Alright, let's get started
- さあ、^{はじ}始めましょう
Okay, let's begin
- じゃあ、^{はじ}始めよう
Well then, let's start
- では、^{はじ}始めましょう
Let's get going
- さあ、いこう
Let's go

Adjusted Expression

A 「それでは、^{はじ}始めましょう」 B 「はい。ところで、^{なに}何から^{はじ}始めますか」

A: Well then, let's begin. B: Yes. By the way, what shall we start with?

Example

A 「さあ、^{はじ}始めよう」 B 「うん、でも、^{なに}何を？」

A: Alright, let's get started. B: Sure, but what should we do?

Notes

"Saa, hajimeyou" is used when the speaker shifts into action and starts something. "Saa" adds momentum, moving the speaker from thinking to doing. In this example, A is ready to begin, but B asks "what?", so the momentum to start and the uncertainty about what to start coexist.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

start starting an action shifting one's mindset prompting momentum

Tags EN

immediate grammar start expression starting an action prompting expression
mindset shift volitional form spoken language

What a relief

ほっとする

Hotto suru

feel relieved

Variants

- ほっとする
feel relieved
- ほっとした
felt relieved
- ほっとして
what a relief
- ほっとしている
that's a relief
- ほっとしたよ
I can finally relax

Adjusted Expression

A 「試験しけんがお終わって、やっと安心あんしんできました」 B 「そうですね。結果けっかがよ良いといいですね」

A: The exam is over, and I can finally relax. B: Yes. I hope the results are good.

Example

A 「試験しけんがお終わった。ほっとした」 B 「うん、結果けっかがよ良かったらいいね」

A: The exam is over. What a relief. B: Yeah, I hope the results are good.

Notes

"Hotto suru" expresses relief when tension or anxiety is released. In this example, A feels lighter because the exam is over. It does not necessarily mean that everything is solved, but that one stage is finally over.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

relief

release of tension

reassurance

change of feeling

settling down

Tags EN

immediate grammar

relief expression

emotional expression

release of tension

reassurance

situation description

spoken language

Whatever it may be

…は何なんであれ

... wa nan de are

whatever ... may be

Variants

- 何なんであれ
whatever it may be
- どんなものであれ
no matter what it is
- 何なんであっても
regardless of what it is
- どのような理由りゆうであれ
whatever the reason may be
- いずれにせよ
in any case

Adjusted Expression

結果けっかがどのようなものであったとしても、それはすでに終わおったことです。

Regardless of what the result was, it is already over.

Example

A 「結果けっかが何なんであれ、もう終わおったことだ」

A: Whatever the result may be, it's already over.

Notes

"... wa nan de are" is used when the speaker makes a judgment regardless of the specific content or condition. In this example, whether the result was good or bad does not matter; the speaker draws a line by saying that it is already over. It is slightly formal, but it helps frame the premise and move the discussion forward.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

regardless of condition inclusiveness generalization introducing a judgment
framing the premise

Tags EN

immediate grammar regardless of condition inclusive expression
generalization expression framing the premise introducing a judgment
slightly formal expression

It'll work out somehow

どうにかなる

Dounika naru

It'll work out somehow

Variants

- どうにかなる
It'll work out somehow
- なんとかなる
It'll be fine
- まあ、なんとかなるさ
Things will turn out okay
- きっと大丈夫 だいじょうぶ
It'll be all right
- どうにかなるよ
We'll manage somehow

Adjusted Expression

状 じょうきょう 況 きび は 厳 げん しい か も し れ ま せ ん が、 最 さい 終 しゅう 的 てき に は 解 かい 決 けつ で き る と お も い ます。

The situation may be difficult, but I think we will eventually be able to resolve it.

Example

A 「締 しめ 切 ぎり に 間 ま に 合 あ う かな...」 B 「大 だい 丈 じょう 夫 ぶ、 だ い じ ょ う ぶ、 どう に かな る よ」

A: Do you think we'll make the deadline? B: Don't worry, it'll work out somehow.

Notes

"Dounika naru" is used to reassure someone or oneself that things will somehow work out, even in a difficult situation. In this example, B responds to anxiety about the deadline with "dounika naru yo." However, if used without any basis, it can sound somewhat irresponsible.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

optimism

reassurance

comfort

encouragement

easing anxiety

Tags EN

immediate grammar

optimistic expression

reassurance expression

comforting expression

encouraging expression

easing anxiety

spoken language

Not all of them

ぜんぶがぜんぶ

Zenbu ga zenbu

not all of them

Variants

- ぜんぶがぜんぶ
not all of them
- すべてがすべて
not everything
- みんながみんな
not everyone is like that
- ^{なに}何もかもがそうってわけじゃない
it is not always the case
- いつもいつもそうとは^{かぎ}限らない
that does not apply to everything

Adjusted Expression

すべての人^{ひと}がそうであるとは言え^いません。

It cannot be said that everyone is like that.

Example

A 「人^{ひと}はみんなそうだよね？」 B 「いや、ぜんぶがぜんぶ、そうってわけじゃないよ」

A: People are all like that, right? B: No, not everyone is like that.

Notes

"Zenbu ga zenbu" is used to push back against a generalization. In this example, B responds to the claim that all people are like that by saying that not everyone is. It does not reject everything, but denies treating all cases as one group.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

partial negation

limiting a generalization

cautiousness

balance

hedging

Tags EN

immediate grammar

partial negation

limiting a generalization

cautious expression

balancing expression

repetition

spoken language

Putting that aside

それはそれとして

Sore wa sore to shite

putting that aside

Variants

- それはそれとして
putting that aside
- それは^お置いといて
that being said
- それはさておき
be that as it may
- ともかくとして
anyway
- まあ、それはそれとして
leaving that aside

Adjusted Expression

その件^{けん}はさておき、次^{つぎ}の問題^{もんだい}に入^{はい}りましょう。

Setting that matter aside, let us move on to the next issue.

Example

「まあ、それはそれとして、今日^{きょう}の予定^{よてい}どうする？」

Anyway, putting that aside, what's the plan for today?

Notes

"Sore wa sore to shite" is used to set the current topic aside and move to another one. In this example, the speaker does not fully reject the previous topic, but leaves it aside and shifts to today's plan. It is a useful topic-shifting expression, though it can also be used to avoid an inconvenient issue.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

topic shift

separation

setting aside

discourse management

concession

Tags EN

immediate grammar

topic shift

separating expression

setting aside

discourse management

discourse marker

spoken language

Some days are just like that

そんな日もある

Sonna hi mo aru

Some days are just like that

Variants

- そんな日もある
Some days are just like that
- そういうこともある
Some days are like that
- まあ、あるよね、そういう日
These things happen
- たまにはそういう日もあるさ
It happens
- そういう日だったんだよ
That's just how it goes sometimes

Adjusted Expression

きょう 今日はうまくいかないことが多おかったです、そういう日もあるものです。

Today did not go well in many ways, but there are days like that.

Example

A 「あー、なんか全然だめだった…」 B 「うん、そんな日もあるよ」

A: Ugh, nothing went right today. B: Yeah, some days are just like that.

Notes

"Sonna hi mo aru" is used to accept a bad day without blaming oneself too much. In this example, B responds to A's feeling that nothing went right by saying that some days are just like that. "Sonna" refers vaguely to the kind of bad or unproductive day that is hard to describe in detail.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

acceptance

comfort

empathy

self-acceptance

settling one's feelings

Tags EN

immediate grammar

acceptance expression

comforting expression

empathy expression

self-acceptance

vague reference

spoken language

For example

たとえば

Tatoeba

For example

Variants

- たとえば
For example
- たとえば、そうだなあ
Well, for instance...
- たとえば...
Say, for example...
- たとえば、ね？
I mean, like...
- たとえば...って言われても
Even if you ask me for an example...

Adjusted Expression

A 「何か例を挙げてください」 B 「たとえば、映画などが考えられます」

A: Please give an example. B: For example, movies may be considered.

Example

A 「何か例をあげてみて」 B 「うーん、たとえば、映画とか？」

A: Can you give me an example? B: Hmm, for example, movies?

Notes

"Tatoeba" is used to make an explanation more concrete by giving an example. In this example, B is thinking and offers "movies?" as a possible example. It can be used not only when the speaker has a clear example, but also when the speaker is searching for one while continuing the conversation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

giving an example

making an explanation concrete

buying time

developing the topic

searching for an example

Tags EN

immediate grammar

example expression

making concrete

buying time

topic development

hesitation

spoken language

It depends

ばあい
場合によりけり

Baai ni yorikeri

It depends

Variants

- ^{ばあい}場合によりけり

It depends

- ^{ばあい}場合によっては

It depends on the case

- ^{じょうきょう}状況しだい

Depending on the situation

- ^{けーす}ケースバイ^{けーす}ケース

Depends on the circumstances

- そのときしだい

Case by case

Adjusted Expression

^{けん}この件については、^{じょうきょう}状況によって^{はんだん}判断が^か変わると^{おも}思います。

Regarding this matter, I think the judgment will depend on the situation.

Example

A 「この^{もんだい}問題、どうする？」 B 「^{ばあい}場合によりけりだね」

A: What should we do about this problem? B: It depends.

Notes

"Baai ni yorikeri" means that the answer or judgment depends on the situation or conditions. In this example, B says "baai ni yorikeri da ne," leaving room to think depending on the case rather than deciding immediately.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

withholding judgment

condition-dependence

cautiousness

flexibility

buying time

Tags EN

immediate grammar

withholding judgment

condition-dependence

cautious expression

flexible expression

buying time

spoken language

While I'm at it

ついでに

Tsuideni

while I'm at it

Variants

- ついでに
while I'm at it
- そのついでに
while I'm there
- ついでと言ってはなんだけど
while you're at it
- はなし話のついでに
as an aside
- い行くついでに
by the way

Adjusted Expression

A 「コンビニへ行くのですか」 B 「はい。必要なものがあれば、あわせて買ってきてみましょうか」

A: Are you going to the convenience store? B: Yes. If you need anything, shall I buy it for you as well?

Example

A 「コンビニ、行くの？」 B 「うん、ついでに何か買って来ようか」

A: Are you going to the convenience store? B: Yeah, do you want me to pick something up while I'm at it?

Notes

"Tsuideni" is used when the speaker adds another action to the main action. In this example, B is already going to the convenience store and offers to buy something for A as well. It works naturally when the added action feels like something that can be done along the same route or occasion.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

addition piggybacking light request supplementing adding an action

Tags EN

immediate grammar addition expression piggybacking expression light request
supplementing expression adding an action spoken language

For now

いちおう
一応

Ichiou

for now

Variants

- いちおう
● 一応

for now

- いちおう かくにん
● 一応、確認だけしとくね

just in case

- いちおう お
● 一応、終わったことにしておこう

tentatively

- いちおう
● 一応はね

kind of

- ねん
● 念のため

for the time being

Adjusted Expression

じゅんび おおむ お かくにん ひつよう
準備は概ね終わりましたが、まだ確認が必要です。

The preparations are mostly complete, but they still need to be checked.

Example

A 「準備できた？」 B 「うん、一応ね」

A: Are you ready? B: Yeah, for now.

Notes

"Ichiou" is used when something is done in a tentative or provisional way, but the speaker still feels some uncertainty. In this example, B says the preparation is done, but "ichiou" leaves room for checking or adjustment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

tentativeness

reservation

modesty

uncertainty

precautionary checking

Tags EN

immediate grammar

tentative expression

reservation expression

modest expression

uncertainty

precautionary checking

spoken language

Anytime

いつでも

Itsudemo

anytime

Variants

- いつでも
anytime
- いつでもいいよ
whenever
- いつでもどうぞ
whenever is fine
- いつでもい言ってね
feel free anytime
- いつでもだいじょうぶ大丈夫
just let me know whenever

Adjusted Expression

ご都合つごうのよいときに、いつでもご連絡れんらくください。

Please feel free to contact me at your convenience.

Example

A 「じゃ、こんどいい？」 B 「うん、いつでも」

A: So, how about next time? B: Yeah, anytime.

Notes

"Itsudemo" is used when the speaker leaves the choice of time to the other person. In this example, B says "itsudemo" to show willingness to fit A's schedule. It does not always mean that every possible time is available; rather, it gives the other person broad room to choose.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

flexibility

acceptance

openness

permission

giving the other person the choice

Tags EN

immediate grammar

response expression

flexible expression

acceptance expression

permission expression

giving the other person the choice

spoken language

Together, always

ずっと、いっしょ

Zutto, issho

together, always

Variants

- ずっと、いっしょ
together, always
- いつまでも、いっしょ
forever together
- これからも、ずっといっしょ
we'll always be together
- ずっと^{いっしょ}にいよう
let's stay together
- これからも^{いっしょ}にいよう
from now on, together

Adjusted Expression

これから^{さき}先も、あなたと^{いっしょ}一緒にいたいと思っ^{おも}ています。

I want to stay with you from now on, always.

Example

A 「これからも？」 B 「うん、ずっと、いっしょ」

A: From now on too? B: Yeah, together, always.

Notes

"Zutto, issho" is a short expression that says the relationship with the other person will continue. In this example, A asks "from now on too?" and B answers "zutto, issho." Instead of explaining in a full sentence, the short form carries affection, commitment, and reassurance at once.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

affection

commitment

reassurance

closeness

confirming continuity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

affection expression

commitment expression

reassurance expression

closeness expression

short utterance

spoken language

Notes

"Sakki" refers to something that happened a short time ago. In this example, the speaker contrasts the rain from a moment ago with the current sunny weather. In conversation, it is also used to bring back something that was said or happened earlier.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

recent past

time reference

resumption

recall

linking the conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

time expression

recent past

resumption expression

recall expression

linking conversation

spoken language

Please wait a bit longer

もう^{すこ}少し、^ま待って

Mou sukoshi, matte

Please wait a bit longer

Variants

- もう^{すこ}少し、^ま待って
Please wait a bit longer
- あとちょっと、^ま待って
Just a little longer
- ちょっとだけ、^ま待って
Wait a bit more
- ^{すこ}少しだけ、^ま待ってて
Hold on a second
- もうちょっとだけ
Just a little more

Adjusted Expression

もう^{すこ}少し^{じかん}時間を^{ただ}いただければ、^{たいおう}対応できます。

If I could have a little more time, I will be able to take care of it.

Example

A 「もう^おすぐ終わるから、もう^{すこ}少し、^ま待って」 B 「うん、^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫だよ」

A: It'll be done soon, so please wait a bit longer. B: Okay, no problem.

Notes

"Mou sukoshi, matte" is used when the speaker wants the other person to wait a little longer. In this example, A is still working on something and asks B to wait, while also saying that it will be done soon. "Mou sukoshi" makes the request softer by suggesting that the wait will not be long.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

request asking for more time time adjustment being in progress

consideration for the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar request expression asking for more time time adjustment

being in progress considerate expression spoken language

A small thing

ちょっとしたこと

Chotto shita koto

a small thing

Variants

- ちょっとしたこと
a small thing
- ちょっとしたこと
just a little thing
- そんなちょっとしたことで
something minor
- ちょっとしたことだけど
over something trivial
- ちょっとしたことがき気になる
a small thing can get to you

Adjusted Expression

ほんのささい些細なことですが、いがい意外にかんたん簡単ではありません。

It is only a small thing, but it is surprisingly not easy.

Example

ちょっとしたことだが、かんたん簡単じゃない。

It's a small thing, but it isn't easy.

Notes

"Chotto shita koto" refers to something that seems small or not worth making a big deal about. In this example, the speaker says that although it looks minor, it is not easy. It can be used either to downplay something or to point out that even a small thing can matter.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

downplaying

modest evaluation

emotional trigger

empathy

reconsideration

Tags EN

immediate grammar

evaluation expression

modest expression

emotional trigger

situation description

small cause

spoken language

I get that

それ、わかる

Sore, wakaru

I get that

Variants

- それ、わかる

I get that

- それ、^{ほんとう}本当にわかる

I totally get that

- まさにそれだよ

I know what you mean

- ^わ分かる、^わ分かる

Exactly

- めっちゃわかる

That really resonates

Adjusted Expression

^{ほんとう}本当にその^{とお}通りで、^{わたし}私も^{おな}同じように(感:)じています。

Exactly. I feel the same way.

Example

A 「この^{じょうきよう}状況、ちょっと^{むずか}難しいね」 B 「うん、それ、わかる」

A: This situation is a bit tough. B: Yeah, I get that.

Notes

"Sore, wakaru" is used to show immediate empathy with the other person's feeling or thought. In this example, B responds to A's sense that the situation is difficult by saying "sore, wakaru." Before giving any explanation, the speaker first accepts and shares the other person's feeling.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

empathy

understanding

agreement

providing reassurance

reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

empathy expression

understanding expression

agreement expression

reassurance

reaction

spoken language

All of a sudden / Out of nowhere

いきなり

Ikinari

All of a sudden / Out of nowhere

Variants

- いきなり
all of a sudden
- いきなり話しかけられた
out of nowhere
- いきなり走り出した
suddenly
- いきなり泣き出した
without warning

Adjusted Expression

とつぜんしつもん 突然質問されると、すぐにはこた答えにくいです。

When someone asks you a question suddenly, it is hard to answer immediately.

Example

いきなりしつもん質問されても、なん何てい言えればいいかね。

Even if you ask me a question all of a sudden, I don't know what to say.

Notes

"Ikinari" is a colloquial expression used when something happens without warning. It often conveys surprise or being caught unprepared, and is more conversational than "totsuzen."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

immediate reaction

sudden change

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

emotion

No thanks

いらない

Iranai

No thanks

Variants

- いらない
No thanks
- もういらない
I don't need it
- ううん、いらない
I'm good
- それは、いらないかな
Not necessary
- いま だいじょうぶ
今は大丈夫
I'm okay for now

Adjusted Expression

きも お気持ちだけいただいております。いま だいじょうぶ 今は大丈夫です。

I appreciate the gesture, but I'm fine for now.

Example

A 「これ、いる？」 B 「ううん、いらない」

A: Do you need this? B: No thanks, I don't need it.

Notes

"Iranai" is a short way to say that something is not needed. In this example, B answers "uun, iranai" to A's offer. It sounds natural in close or casual situations, but depending on tone, it can sound a little strong, so expressions like "I'm okay for now" can soften the refusal.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

refusal

restraint

saying something is unnecessary

avoiding acceptance

soft refusal

Tags EN

immediate grammar

refusal expression

restraint expression

unnecessary expression

soft refusal

response expression

spoken language

Awkward

き
気まずい

Kimazui

awkward

Variants

- 気まずい
awkward
- ちょっと気まずいね
a bit awkward
- なんか空気が重い
the atmosphere feels heavy
- 気まずくなった
things got awkward
- ちょっと気まずい雰囲気になった
it became a little uncomfortable

Adjusted Expression

ふたり あいだ き ふんいき う
二人の間に、少し気まずい雰囲気が生まれてしまいました。

A slightly awkward atmosphere arose between the two of them.

Example

A 「昨日の話、気まずいね」 B 「うん、ちょっとね」

A: Yesterday's conversation was awkward, wasn't it? B: Yeah, a bit.

Notes

"Kimazui" is used when an awkward or uncomfortable atmosphere arises between people. In this example, something about yesterday's conversation still feels difficult to talk about. It can be used even when there is no major conflict, but silence or misunderstanding makes the situation feel strained.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

awkwardness interpersonal relationship atmosphere silence discomfort
misunderstanding

Tags EN

immediate grammar interpersonal relationship emotional expression
situation description atmosphere silence spoken language

Before I knew it

気がついたら

Ki ga tsuitara

Before I knew it

Variants

- 気がついたら
Before I knew it
- いつの間にか
When I realized it
- 知らないうちに
Before I noticed
- ふと気づくと
Suddenly I noticed
- 気づいたら
Without realizing it

Adjusted Expression

知らないうちに時間が過ぎていて、もう夏休みになっていました。

Time had passed without my realizing it, and it was already summer vacation.

Example

A 「気がついたら、もう夏休みだね」 B 「うん、早いね」

A: Before I knew it, it's already summer vacation. B: Yeah, time flies.

Notes

"Ki ga tsuitara" is used when the speaker realizes afterward that time has passed or the situation has changed without noticing. In this example, A realizes that it is already summer vacation. It suggests not a planned change, but a later realization: "Oh, already?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

realization

passage of time

unconsciousness

surprise

change of situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

realization expression

passage of time

unconsciousness

change of situation

surprise

spoken language

Completely

すっかり

Sukkari

completely

Variants

- すっかり
completely
- かんぜん完全に
entirely
- まるっきり
totally
- すっかりわす忘れてた
I completely forgot
- すっかりか変わった
it changed completely

Adjusted Expression

A 「しゅくだい宿題は終わりましたか」 B 「すみません。しゅくだい宿題のかんぜんことをわす完全に忘れていました」

A: Did you finish your homework? B: I'm sorry. I completely forgot about the homework.

Example

A 「しゅくだい宿題、お終わった？」 B 「ああ、しゅくだい宿題ね、わすすっかり、忘れてた」

A: Did you finish your homework? B: Oh, the homework? I completely forgot about it.

Notes

"Sukkari" means that something is completely in a certain state. In this example, the homework had completely slipped from the speaker's mind. It can also describe change or completion, but in "sukkari wasureteta," it also carries the speaker's small surprise at realizing it.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

completeness

completion

change of state

forgetting

surprise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

completeness expression

change of state

forgetting expression

surprise

spoken language

That's what I wanted to say

い
言いたいんだよ、それが

Iitai n da yo, sore ga

That's what I wanted to say

Variants

- 言いたいんだよ、それが
That's what I wanted to say
- 言いたいの、それが
Exactly, that's it
- まさに言いたかった、それが
That's the point I was trying to make
- それが言いたかったんだよ
That's exactly what I mean
- そう、それが言いたい
Yes, that's what I mean

Adjusted Expression

わたし
私が言いたかったのは、それです。

That is what I wanted to say.

Example

A 「言いたいんだよ、それが」 B 「うん、分かるよ」

A: That's what I wanted to say. B: Yeah, I get it.

Notes

"iitai n da yo, sore ga" is an inverted expression. The speaker first says "that's what I want to say" and then adds "sore ga" to mark the focus. The regular order would be "sore ga iitai n da yo," but in conversation the feeling or reaction may come first. Keeping the particle "ga" after "sore" makes the focus clear.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis realization shared feeling focusing rephrasing

Tags EN

immediate grammar inversion predicate-first structure focusing
emotional expression empathy expression spoken language

My heart was pounding

どきどきした

Dokidoki shita

My heart was pounding

Variants

- どきどきした

My heart was pounding

- むね胸がどきどきした

My heart was racing

- しんぞう心臓がぼくぼくした

My heart thumped

Adjusted Expression

きんちょう緊張して、しんぞう心臓がどきどきしました。

I was so nervous that my heart was pounding.

Example

A 「はじ初めてのでーとデートで、どきどきした」

A: My heart was pounding on my first date.

Notes

"Dokidoki shita" expresses the feeling of a pounding heart caused by nervousness, anticipation, or anxiety. It can be used in both happy and uneasy situations, and its immediacy comes from turning a bodily sensation directly into an emotional expression.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

nervousness

anticipation

anxiety

Tags EN

immediate grammar

emotion

physical sensation

context-dependent

I'm excited

わくわくする

Wakuwaku suru

I'm excited

Variants

- わくわくする
I'm excited
- わくわくしている
I feel thrilled
- ^{むね}胸がわくわくする
I'm really looking forward to it
- ^{たの}楽しみでわくわくする

Adjusted Expression

とても^{たの}楽しみにしています。

I am very much looking forward to it.

Example

A 「^{むすこ}息子は、^{あす}明日、^{きゅうじょう}球場に行けるので、^いわくわくしているよ」

A: My son is excited because he can go to the stadium tomorrow.

Notes

"Wakuwaku suru" expresses the rising feeling of excitement when looking forward to something. It is an immediate way of putting positive

anticipation into words. For another person's feelings, "wakuwaku shite iru" is more natural, while for your own feelings both "wakuwaku suru" and "wakuwaku shite iru" can be used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

anticipation enjoyment excitement

Tags EN

immediate grammar emotion physical sensation context-dependent

That makes me nervous

ひやひやする

Hiyahiya suru

That makes me nervous

Variants

- ひやひやする
That makes me nervous
- ^み見^ていてひやひやする
It makes me anxious
- ^ひ冷^{あせ}や^で汗が出る
It makes me break into a cold sweat
- ^{あぶ}危^なっかしくてひやひやする
I'm on edge watching it

Adjusted Expression

^{みち}道^{こお}が凍^{あぶ}っていて危^{ある}ないので、歩^ふくときにと^あても不安^{ふあん}です。

The road is frozen and dangerous, so I feel very nervous when walking on it.

Example

A 「^{みち}道^{こお}が凍^{あぶ}っていて、歩^{ある}くのがひやひやするね」

A: The road is frozen, so walking on it makes me nervous.

Notes

"Hiyahiya suru" is used when the speaker feels anxious or tense because a situation seems dangerous. In this example, walking on the frozen road feels risky. It does not mean that an accident has happened, but that something might happen, making the speaker uneasy.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

anxiety worry nervousness sense of danger watching anxiously

Tags EN

immediate grammar emotional expression physical sensation anxiety expression
sense of danger situation description spoken language

Oops

しまった

Shimatta

Oops

Variants

- しまった

Oops

- あ、しまった

Oh no

- うわ、しまった

Damn

- しまった、^{わす}忘れた

I messed up

- やってしまった

I forgot

Adjusted Expression

^{しっばい}失敗してしまいました。

I made a mistake.

Example

A 「あ、しまった」 B 「どうしたの」 A 「^{けいたい}携帯、^{わす}忘れた」

A: Oops. B: What happened? A: I forgot my phone.

Notes

"Shimatta" is a short reaction used at the moment the speaker realizes a mistake or something forgotten. In this example, A realizes that they forgot their phone and says "a, shimatta" before explaining the situation. The regret or panic comes out before the explanation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

regret realization mistake panic immediate reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar mistake expression regret expression realization expression
emotional expression reaction expression spoken language

If possible

できれば

Dekireba

If possible

Variants

- できれば
If possible
- もしできれば
If you can
- できたら
If it's okay
- できればでいいんだけど
If possible, by today
- できればきょうじゅう今日中に
Only if you can

Adjusted Expression

もしかのう可能であれば、きょうじゅう今日中ねがにお願いします。

If possible, please do it by the end of today.

Example

A 「できれば、きょうじゅう今日中ねがにお願い」 B 「わかった、やってみる」

A: If possible, by today. B: Okay, I'll try.

Notes

"Dekireba" softens a hope or request. In this example, A gives the deadline "by today," but adding "dekireba" makes it sound less like a direct order and more considerate of the other person's situation. Even so, it may still carry a fairly strong expectation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

hope request politeness giving a deadline reducing pressure

Tags EN

immediate grammar request expression hope expression polite hesitation
deadline expression considerate expression spoken language

I ate too much

た
食べすぎた

Tabesugita

I ate too much

Variants

- た食べすぎた

I ate too much

- た食べすぎちゃった

I overate

- た食べすぎってしまった

I ended up eating too much

- た食べすぎたかも

Maybe I ate too much

- た食べすぎでくる苦しい

I ate so much it hurts

Adjusted Expression

おも
思ったよりも多くおお た食べてしまいました。

I ended up eating more than I expected.

Example

A 「どうしたの？」 B 「た食べすぎた。くる苦しい」

A: What's wrong? B: I ate too much. It hurts.

Notes

"Tabesugita" is used when the speaker realizes after eating that they ate too much and feels a little regret. In this example, B adds "kurushii," showing that the bodily sensation and regret come before any detailed explanation. It is not a serious mistake, but a small everyday regret.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

regret

realization

physical sensation

self-explanation

minor mistake

Tags EN

immediate grammar

regret expression

realization expression

physical sensation

minor mistake

self-explanation

spoken language

Books and magazines and stuff

ほん ざっし
本とか雑誌とか、...

Hon toka zasshi toka,...

Books and magazines and stuff...

Variants

- ...とか...
...and...and...
- ...とか...とか
...or...or...
- ...など
...and stuff
- ...や...など
...such as...
- ...なり...
...things like...

Adjusted Expression

ほん ざっし せいり
本や雑誌などを整理しました。

I sorted out books, magazines, and such.

Example

A 「全部、捨てちゃったの？」 B 「ああ、ほん ざっし
本とか雑誌とか...いろいろ」

A: Did you throw everything away? B: Yeah, books, magazines, and all sorts of stuff...

Notes

"...toka...toka" is used to give examples without listing everything precisely. In this example, the speaker mentions books and magazines, while leaving room for other things as well. It both lists examples and keeps the details vague.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

listing

giving examples

vagueness

skipping details

leaving room

Tags EN

immediate grammar

listing expression

example expression

vague expression

skipping details

spoken language

That's not true

そんなことないって

Sonna koto nai tte

That's not true

Variants

- そんなことないって
That's not true
- そんなことないよ
No way
- そんなことないから
It's not like that
- そんなことないってば
That's not true, really
- だいじょうぶ大丈夫、そんなことないよ
Don't say that

Adjusted Expression

そのように^{かんが}考える^{ひつよう}必要はない^{おも}と思います。

I do not think you need to think of it that way.

Example

A わたし「私、なに何^だやっても^だダメなんだよね」 B 「そんなことないって！」

A: I feel like I fail at everything. B: That's not true!

Notes

"Sonna koto nai tte" is used to respond quickly to someone's negative statement and gently deny it. In this example, B says it to A, who is blaming themselves. Before giving any explanation, B offers reassurance by saying that it is not true.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

negation

encouragement

empathy

reassurance

responding to self-denial

Tags EN

immediate grammar

negation expression

encouraging expression

empathy expression

reassurance expression

reaction expression

spoken language

I hope so

だったらいいけど...

Dattara ii kedo...

I hope so...

Variants

- だったらいいけど...
I hope so...
- そうだったらいいけど
That would be nice...
- そうならいいけど
It'd be great if that were true...
- そうだといいけど
I wish that were true...
- ほんとう本当にそうならいいけど
If only that were true...

Adjusted Expression

そうであれば嬉しいのですが、まだ確信はありません。

It would make me happy if that were the case, but I am not sure yet.

Example

A 「あした明日はは晴れるかな」 B 「だったらいいけど...」

A: Do you think it'll be sunny tomorrow? B: I hope so...

Notes

"Dattara ii kedo..." is used when the speaker hopes something is true, but cannot fully believe it yet. In this example, B hopes it will be sunny, but still feels unsure. Ending with "kedo" leaves the hesitation unfinished.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

hope

uncertainty

hesitation

wish

half-belief

Tags EN

immediate grammar

hope expression

uncertainty expression

tentative expression

unfinished utterance

wish

spoken language

Sorry, sorry

ごめんごめん

Gomen gomen

Sorry, sorry

Variants

- ごめんごめん

Sorry, sorry

- あ、ごめんごめん

Oh, sorry

- ごめんね

Sorry about that

- ごめんごめんね

Oops, sorry

- わる悪い、わる悪い

My bad

Adjusted Expression

もう申し訳わけありません。き気づきませんでした。

I'm sorry. I didn't notice.

Example

A 「あれ？どドアあし閉めた？」 B 「ごめんごめん、し閉めてくるね」

A: Did you close the door? B: Sorry, sorry. I'll go close it.

Notes

"Gomen gomen" is a casual apology used when the speaker notices a small mistake. In this example, B realizes that the door was not closed and quickly says "gomen gomen." The repetition makes it feel like an immediate, light apology rather than a serious one.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

apology light apology realization slight awkwardness correction

Tags EN

immediate grammar apology expression light apology repetition

realization expression correction expression spoken language

I don't know

わかんない

Wakannai

I don't know

Variants

- わかんない
I don't know
- ^わ分からない
I'm not sure
- うーん、わかんない
I have no idea
- さあ、わかんない
I don't really know
- ^{ぜんぜん}全然わかんない
I don't understand at all

Adjusted Expression

すみません。よく^わ分かりません。

I'm sorry. I'm not sure.

Example

A 「これ、どうやって^{つか}使うの？」 B 「わかんない」

A: How do you use this? B: I don't know.

Notes

"Wakannai" is a casual contracted form of "wakaranai," meaning "I don't know" or "I don't understand." In this example, B answers immediately when asked how to use something. It sounds natural in close or informal situations, but depending on tone, it can sound a little blunt.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

negation

not knowing

hesitation

immediate response

lack of understanding

Tags EN

immediate grammar

negative expression

not-knowing expression

lack of understanding

contracted expression

light response

spoken language

I think they came

来たんじゃない？

Kita n ja nai?

I think they came

Variants

- 来たんじゃない？
I think they came
- 来たんじゃないかな？
Maybe they came
- 来たと思うよ
They probably came
- 来たんじゃない？
Aren't they already here?
- もう来てるんじゃない？
I think they're already here

Adjusted Expression

もう来ているのではないのでしょうか。

I think they may already be here.

Example

A 「もうみんな集まった？」 B 「来たんじゃない？」

A: Is everyone here already? B: I think they came.

Notes

"Kita n ja nai?" gives a tentative assessment that someone probably came, without stating it as a firm fact. In this example, B has not fully checked whether everyone is there, but lightly suggests that they probably came. The expression leaves room for the listener to confirm.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

supposition

confirmation

shared understanding

assessment

light question

Tags EN

immediate grammar

supposition expression

confirmation expression

question

assessment

sharing

spoken language

Oh, I see

そっか

Sokka

Oh, I see

Variants

- そっか
Oh, I see
- そっかそっか
I see
- そっかー
I get it
- ああ、そっか
Ah, okay
- そういふことか
So that's what it means

Adjusted Expression

そうですか。わかりました。

I see. I understand.

Example

A 「もう帰^{かえ}ったよ」 B 「そっか」

A: They already left. B: Oh, I see.

Notes

"Sokka" is a short reaction used when understanding or realization happens in the moment. In this example, B receives the information that someone already left and responds with "sokka." It does not explain much, but lightly shows that the speaker has understood and accepted the information.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

understanding realization comprehension backchannel acceptance

Tags EN

immediate grammar realization expression understanding expression
comprehension expression backchannel reaction expression spoken language

Looks like it's over

お
終わったっぽい

Owatta ppoi

Looks like it's over

Variants

- お終わったっぽい
Looks like it's over
- お終わったみたい
Seems like it's over
- もう終わったっぽい
I think it's over
- お終わった感じ
Looks like it's finished
- お終わってるっぽい
It seems to be done

Adjusted Expression

お終わったようです。

It seems to have ended.

Example

A 「まだやってる？」 B 「お終わったっぽいよ」

A: Is it still going? B: Looks like it's over.

Notes

"Owatta ppoi" is used when the speaker has not confirmed something clearly, but judges from the situation or impression that it seems to be over. In this example, B does not state it as a fact, but gives a light assessment. The suffix "ppoi" adds uncertainty and a casual tone.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

supposition

confirmation

impression

light judgment

sharing

Tags EN

immediate grammar

supposition expression

impression expression

confirmation expression

light judgment

suffix

spoken language

Apparently

らしい

Rashii

apparently

Variants

- ...らしい
apparently
- ...らしいよ
it seems
- ...らしいね
I heard
- ...らしいです
they say
- そうらしい
that's what I heard

Adjusted Expression

ええ、そのようにき聞いています。

Yes, that's what I heard.

Example

A 「あの店、みせ閉店へいてんなの？」 B 「うん、そうらしい」

A: Is that shop closing? B: Yeah, apparently.

Notes

"Rashii" is used to share information heard from others or judged from the situation without stating it as a firm fact. In this example, B has not directly confirmed that the shop is closing, but responds with "sou rashii" as hearsay. It shares the information while keeping some distance from full certainty.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

hearsay

supposition

sharing

avoiding assertion

confirmation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

hearsay expression

supposition expression

sharing information

avoiding assertion

response expression

spoken language

In that case

となると

To naru to

In that case

Variants

- となると
In that case
- そうなると
If that's the case
- じゃあ、となると
Then
- それなら
That means
- だとすると
If so

Adjusted Expression

そういうことになりますと、かいぎ えんき会議は延期になるかもしれません。

If that is the case, the meeting may be postponed.

Example

A 「たなか田中さん、あすこ明日来ないって」 B 「となると、かいぎ えんき会議は延期かな」

A: Tanaka-san says he won't come tomorrow. B: In that case, the meeting might be postponed.

Notes

"To naru to" is used when the speaker takes the previous information and moves to the next judgment or conclusion. In this example, B hears that Tanaka-san will not come and infers that the meeting may be postponed. It is a reaction that organizes the situation and considers what follows.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

inference

organizing the situation

conditional judgment

moving to a conclusion

next judgment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

inference expression

organizing the situation

conditional judgment

discourse marker

introducing a conclusion

spoken language

Yeah, that happens

あるある

Aru aru

Yeah, that happens

Variants

- あるある
Yeah, that happens
- うん、あるある
Yeah, I've had that experience
- それ、あるある
That happens to me too
- あるよ
I know what you mean
- ^わ分かる、あるある
I've been there

Adjusted Expression

そういう^{けいけん}経験はあります。

I have had that kind of experience.

Example

A 「そういう^{けいけん}経験、ある？」 B 「あるある」

A: Have you had that kind of experience? B: Yeah, that happens.

Notes

"Aru aru" is used when the speaker immediately empathizes by saying that they have had a similar experience. In this example, B answers quickly with "aru aru," showing shared experience. The repetition makes it more than a simple "yes"; it becomes a reaction like "that happens" or "I know what you mean."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation of experience

empathy

immediate response

sharing

reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

empathy expression

sharing experience

immediate reaction vocabulary

repetition

backchannel

spoken language

Piece of cake

あさめしまえ
朝飯前

Asameshimae

Piece of cake

Variants

- あさめしまえ
朝飯前

Piece of cake

- あさめしまえ
朝飯前だよ

It's easy

- あさめしまえ
そんな朝飯前

No sweat

- かんたん
簡単だよ

It's nothing

- らくしょう
楽勝だよ

I can do it easily

Adjusted Expression

かんたん
簡単にできます。

I can do it easily.

Example

A 「このもんだい問題、できる？」 B 「あさめしまえ朝飯前だよ」

A: Can you solve this problem? B: Piece of cake.

Notes

"Asameshimae" is an idiom meaning that something is very easy, like "piece of cake." In this example, B answers with confidence that the problem is easy to solve. Although "meshi" is a casual word for a meal, "asameshimae" is a fixed idiom and should not be changed to "asagohan mae."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

ease

confidence

self-assurance

immediate response

light assessment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

assessment expression

ease

confidence expression

immediate response

idiom

spoken language

Right

ですね

Desu ne

Right

Variants

- ですね
Right
- そうですね
Yeah
- ですねー
That's true
- ええ、ですね
It is
- ほんとう 本当ですね
Sure is

Adjusted Expression

そうですね。 ほんとう 本あつ当あつに暑あついあつですね。

That's true. It really is hot.

Example

A 「あつ暑あついあつですね」 B 「ですね」

A: It's hot, isn't it? B: Right.

Notes

"Desu ne" is a short response that lightly shows agreement or empathy with what the other person has just said. In this example, B immediately responds to A's "It's hot, isn't it?" with "desu ne." Rather than adding new information, it accepts the other person's feeling and keeps the conversation going.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

agreement

acknowledgment

empathy

backchannel

keeping the conversation going

Tags EN

immediate grammar

backchannel

agreement expression

empathy expression

acknowledgment expression

keeping conversation going

spoken language

So what?

だったら？

Dattara?

So what?

Variants

- だったら？
So what?
- それで？
And?
- だから？
Then what?
- もしそうなら？
If so, then what?
- だったらどうするの？
What are you going to do about it?

Adjusted Expression

もしそうであれば、どうするつもりですか。

If that is the case, what are you going to do?

Example

A 「それ、^{ぜったい}絶対、^{まちが}間違ってるよ」 B 「だったら？」

A: That's definitely wrong. B: So what?

Notes

"Dattara?" is used to question back after hearing the other person's statement, meaning something like "if so, then what?" In this example, B responds immediately to A's claim that something is wrong. It is a short reaction, but depending on tone, it can sound quite challenging.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

rebuttal

questioning back

provocation

asking for clarification

challenge

Tags EN

immediate grammar

questioning-back expression

rebuttal expression

challenge expression

provocation

short reply

spoken language

That again

それ、ばっかり

Sore, bakkari

That again

Variants

- それ、ばっかり
That again
- そればかりじゃん
Always that
- またそれ
Just that
- そればかり
You're always doing that
- いつもそれだね
It's always the same thing

Adjusted Expression

いつもおな同じことばかりですね。

It is always the same thing.

Example

A 「ねえ、らーめんラーメン、た食べに行こ？」 B 「それ、ばっかり」

A: Hey, let's go eat ramen. B: That again.

Notes

"Sore, bakkari" is used when the speaker feels that the other person's topic or action is always the same. In this example, A suggests ramen again, and B responds with "sore, bakkari." It is a short reaction, but it carries light exasperation or dissatisfaction.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

criticism

exasperation

pointing out

dissatisfaction

reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

pointing-out expression

criticism expression

exasperation expression

dissatisfaction expression

pointing out a bias

spoken language

No matter what

どうしても

Doushitemo

no matter what

Variants

- どうしても
no matter what
- どうしても無理むり
I just can't
- どうしても必要ひつよう
I really need it
- どうしてもやりたい
I absolutely want to do it
- どうしても行けないい
I really can't go

Adjusted Expression

どうしても行くことができません。

I really cannot go.

Example

A 「来れないの？」 B 「うん、どうしても」

A: Can't you come? B: No, I really can't.

Notes

"Doushitemo" shows that the speaker's feeling or circumstances are strong and cannot easily be changed. In this example, B does not explain the reason in detail, but simply says "doushitemo." Depending on context, it can express a strong wish, as in "I really need it," or a strong refusal, as in "I really can't."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis

determination

inevitability

explaining circumstances

refusal

Tags EN

immediate grammar

emphasis expression

determination expression

inevitability

refusal expression

explaining circumstances

spoken language

Can I...?

～てもいい？

...temo ii?

Can I...?

Variants

- ^み見てもいい？
Can I look?
- ^た食べてもいい？
Can I eat it?
- ^{はい}入ってもいい？
Can I come in?
- ^{つか}使ってもいい？
Can I use it?
- ちょっと^み見てもいい？
Is it okay if I take a quick look?

Adjusted Expression

それを見てもよろしいですか。

Would it be all right if I looked at that?

Example

A 「それ、^み見てもいい？」 B 「うん、いいよ」

A: Can I look at that? B: Sure.

Notes

"...temo ii?" is used to ask for permission before doing something. In this example, A asks whether it is okay to look at something. It sounds natural in close or casual situations, while "...temo yoroshii desu ka?" is safer in formal settings.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

permission

checking

request

consideration for the listener

checking before acting

Tags EN

immediate grammar

permission expression

request expression

checking expression

considerate expression

question expression

spoken language

Might be nice

いいかも

Ii kamo

Might be nice

Variants

- いいかも
Might be nice
- それ、いいかも
That might be good
- いいかもしれない
Could be nice
- けっこういいかも
Sounds like a good idea
- それ、ありかも
That could work

Adjusted Expression

それは良い案よ あんかもしれませんね。

That might be a good idea.

Example

A 「ちょっと遠出とおでしてみる？」 B 「それ、いいかも」

A: Wanna go for a little trip? B: That might be nice.

Notes

"Ii kamo" is used to respond positively but softly to a suggestion. In this example, B says "sore, ii kamo," accepting the idea of going on a short trip in a positive way. The "kamo" keeps the response from sounding too definite and leaves a little room for thought.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

judgment soft agreement shared feeling possibility accepting a suggestion

Tags EN

immediate grammar assessment expression soft agreement tentative expression
response to a suggestion possibility expression spoken language

What is that!?

なに
何、それ！

Nani, sore!

What is that!?

Variants

- なに
何、それ！
What is that!?
- なにそれ！
What the heck is that?
- なに
何それ！
Seriously?
- え、なに
何それ！
No way!
- なに
何、それ、ひどくない？
That's terrible, isn't it?

Adjusted Expression

それはどういうことですか。

What does that mean?

Example

A 「あんなに親切しんせつにしたのに、何もなに言いわないんだよ」 B 「何なに、それ！」

A: I was so nice to him, but he didn't say anything. B: What is that!?

Notes

"Nani, sore!" is an immediate reaction of surprise or exasperation to what the other person has said. In this example, B is not really asking for the name of something, but reacting with a feeling like "that's terrible." It is not a neutral question about meaning, but an emotional response that comes first.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

empathy

exasperation

emotional reaction

aligning with the speaker

Tags EN

immediate grammar

emotional expression

exclamatory expression

surprise expression

empathy expression

immediate reaction vocabulary

spoken language

Not that far

...まではね

...made wa ne

not that far

Variants

- そこまではね
Not that far
- やるけど...そこまではね
I can do it, but not that far
- 行くけど...泊まりまではね
I'm okay up to a point
- 手伝うけど...全部まではね
That's a bit too much for me
- そこまではちょっと
I can go, but staying over is a bit much

Adjusted Expression

それ以上は、少し難しいです。

Going beyond that would be a little difficult.

Example

A 「じゃ、いっしょに泊まって行こうよ」 B 「うーん、泊まりまではね...」

A: Then let's stay over together. B: Hmm... staying over is a bit too much.

Notes

"...made wa ne" is used to show that something is acceptable up to a certain point, but going beyond that is difficult. In this example, B does not reject going together, but sets a boundary by saying "tomari made wa ne..." It is an unfinished, soft way to refuse while still considering the other person.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

hesitation

limitation

setting a boundary

soft refusal

consideration

Tags EN

immediate grammar

limiting expression

hesitation expression

setting a boundary

soft refusal

unfinished utterance

spoken language

Even if I have to...

...^{ても}

...*te demo*

even if I have to...

Variants

- ^い行ってでも
even if I have to go
- ^{はら}払ってでも
even if I have to pay
- ^{うば}奪ってでも
even if I have to take it
- ^な泣いてでも
even if I have to cry
- ^{むり}無理してでも
even if I have to push myself

Adjusted Expression

たとえ^{たいきん}大金を支^{しはら}払うことになっても、^て手に入^いれたいです。

Even if I have to pay a large amount of money, I want to get it.

Example

A 「その^{ほん}本、もう手に入^{はい}らないよ」 B 「^{たいきん}大金を支^{しはら}払ってでも手に入^てれたい！」

A: That book is no longer available. B: I want to get it, even if I have to pay a lot of money!

Notes

"...te demo" is used when the speaker wants to achieve a goal even by using a difficult or costly means. In this example, B says they want to get the book even if they have to pay a lot of money. It emphasizes that the goal is more important than the cost or effort.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

strong will

prioritizing the goal

emphasizing the means

determination

sacrifice

Tags EN

immediate grammar

will expression

prioritizing the goal

emphasizing the means

determination expression

sacrifice expression

spoken language

You were there for me

...てくれたね

...te kureta ne

You did that for me, didn't you?

Variants

- ^{てっだ}手伝ってくれたね
You helped me, didn't you?
- ^ま待っててくれたね
You waited for me, didn't you?
- ^{おぼ}覚えててくれたね
You remembered, didn't you?
- ^{いっしょ}一緒にいてくれたね
You were there with me, weren't you?
- いつもいてくれたね
You were always there for me.

Adjusted Expression

いつも^{いっしょ}一緒にいてくれて、ありがとうございました。

Thank you for always being with me.

Example

A 「いつも、^{いっしょ}一緒にいてくれたね」 B 「^{いっしょ}ぼくが一緒にいたかっただけだよ」

A: You were always there with me, weren't you? B: I just wanted to be with you.

Notes

"...te kureta ne" is used to receive what someone did for the speaker with gratitude or closeness. In this example, A says "issho ni ite kureta ne," looking back with appreciation on the fact that the other person was there. Rather than directly saying "thank you," it gently recalls the time they shared.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude

recollection

shared memory

closeness

receiving the other person's action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

gratitude expression

recollection expression

closeness expression

shared-memory expression

auxiliary verb

spoken language

You waited for me

ま
待っててくれたんだ

Mattete kureta n da

You waited for me

Variants

- ま待っててくれたんだ
You waited for me
- ま待っててくれたね
You were waiting for me
- ま待っててくれたの？
You stayed and waited for me
- ま待ってくれてたんだ
Were you waiting for me?
- ま待っててくれてたんだ
You'd been waiting for me

Adjusted Expression

まお待ちくださり、どうもありがとうございます。

Thank you very much for waiting.

Example

A 「試験しけん、どうだった？」 B 「ああ、ま待っててくれたんだ」

A: How was the exam? B: Oh, you waited for me.

Notes

"Mattete kureta n da" is used when the speaker realizes that the other person waited for them and receives that action with gratitude or warmth. In this example, B realizes from A's question that A had been waiting. The ending "n da" adds a sense of realization and slight surprise.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude realization surprise closeness receiving the other person's care

Tags EN

immediate grammar gratitude expression realization expression surprise expression
closeness expression auxiliary verb spoken language

You remembered

おぼ
覚えててくれたんだ

Oboetete kureta n da

You remembered

Variants

- ^{おぼ}覚えててくれたんだ
You remembered
- ^{おぼ}覚えててくれたね
You remembered it for me
- ^{おぼ}覚えててくれたの？
You remembered, didn't you?
- ^{おぼ}覚えてくれてたんだ
Did you remember?
- ^{おぼ}覚えててくれてたんだ
You had remembered it for me

Adjusted Expression

^{おぼ}覚えていてくださって、ありがとうございます。

Thank you for remembering.

Example

A 「^{たんじょうび}誕生日、^{おぼ}覚えててくれたんだ」 B 「もちろんだよ」

A: You remembered my birthday. B: Of course I did.

Notes

"Oboetete kureta n da" is used when the speaker realizes that the other person remembered something important. In this example, A realizes that the other person remembered their birthday and receives that with gratitude and happiness. The ending "n da" adds a sense of realization and slight surprise.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude realization surprise closeness receiving the other person's thoughtfulness

Tags EN

immediate grammar gratitude expression realization expression surprise expression
closeness expression auxiliary verb spoken language

About earlier, I may have said too much

さっき、^い言いすぎたかも

Sakki, iisugita kamo

About earlier, I may have said too much

Variants

- さっき、^い言いすぎたかも
About earlier, I may have said too much
- さっきは、ちょっと^い言いすぎたかも
I may have gone too far earlier
- さっきのことだけど、^い言いすぎたかな
About what I said earlier, maybe I said too much
- さっきはごめん
Sorry about earlier
- さっきの^い言^{かた}い方、きつかったかも
Maybe I sounded a bit harsh earlier

Adjusted Expression

さきほどは、少し^い言いすぎたかもしれません。

Earlier, I may have said a little too much.

Example

A 「さっき、^い言いすぎたかも」 B 「ううん、^き気にしてないよ」

A: I may have said too much earlier. B: No, don't worry about it.

Notes

"Sakki, iisugita kamo" is used when the speaker looks back on something they said earlier and realizes that they may have gone too far. In this example, A does not begin with a direct apology, but softly corrects their own wording. Here, "sakki" is not just a time reference; it becomes an entry point into apology and repairing the relationship.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

introducing an apology self-correction realization repairing the relationship
soft checking

Tags EN

immediate grammar introducing an apology self-correction realization expression
repairing the relationship saying too much spoken language

Since earlier

さっきから

Sakki kara

since earlier

Variants

- さっきから
since earlier
- さっきからずっと
this whole time
- さっきから^き気になってた
I've been wondering since earlier
- さっきから^み見てたよ
I've been watching you for a while
- さっきから^い言おうと^{おも}思ってた
I've been meaning to say this for a while

Adjusted Expression

さきほどから、^い言おうと^{おも}思っていたことがあります。

There is something I have been meaning to say since earlier.

Example

A 「さっきから、^い言おうと^{おも}思ってたんだけど...」 B 「うん、なに？」

A: I've been meaning to say this for a while. B: Yeah? What is it?

Notes

"Sakki kara" is used to bring out a thought or feeling that has continued from a short while ago until now. In this example, A begins to say something that they had been meaning to say. It is not only about the length of time, but about something that had been lingering inside and is now becoming words.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

continuity

awareness

emotional buildup

opening a topic

expressing an internal state

Tags EN

immediate grammar

time expression

continuity expression

emotional buildup

topic-opening expression

internal state

spoken language

It looks like...

...みたい

...mitai

it looks like...

Variants

- ^{あめ}雨みたい
looks like rain
- ^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫みたい
seems okay
- ^おもう終わったみたい
looks like it's already over
- ^{じこ}事故みたい
looks like an accident
- ...みたいなんだけど
it seems like...

Adjusted Expression

^{じこ}事故があったようです。

It appears that there was an accident.

Example

A ^{ひと}「人、^{あつ}集まってるね」 B ^{じこ}「なんか、事故みたい」

A: People are gathering there. B: Looks like there was an accident or something.

Notes

"...mitai" is used to express an impression based on what the speaker sees or senses, without making a firm statement. In this example, B sees people gathering and says it looks like an accident. It is not a definite statement, but an assessment made from the situation in the moment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

guess

observation

impression

withholding certainty

sharing information

Tags EN

immediate grammar

guessing expression

observation expression

impression expression

withholding certainty

sharing information

spoken language

Apparently / It seems...

...らしい

...rashii

apparently / it seems...

Variants

- ^{あめ}雨らしい
apparently
- ^{てすと}テストは^{あした}明日らしい
it seems like rain
- もう^お終わったらしいよ
apparently the test is tomorrow
- なんか、^{じこ}事故があったらしい
looks like it's already over
- ^{ちよくせつ き}直接聞いたわけじゃないんだけど、...らしい
I didn't hear it directly, but apparently...

Adjusted Expression

...とのことですよ。

According to what I heard, ...

Example

A 「^{えき}駅、^こすごく混んでたよ」 B 「なんか、^{じこ}事故があったらしい」

A: The station was really crowded. B: Apparently, there was some kind of accident.

Notes

"...rashii" is used to share information that the speaker has not directly confirmed, or an assessment based on the situation, without making a firm assertion. In this example, B guesses and shares the possible reason why the station was crowded. The lead-in expression "nanka" helps the following "jiko ga atta rashii" arise as an assessment rather than a firm statement.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

hearsay

inference

assessment

avoiding assertion

sharing information

Tags EN

immediate grammar

hearsay expression

inference expression

assessment

avoiding assertion

sharing information

lead-in chain

Quite / Pretty

かなり

Kanari

quite / pretty

Variants

- かなりいい
pretty good
- かなり^{つか}疲れた
quite tired
- かなり^{むづか}難しかった
fairly difficult
- かなり^{たいへん}大変だった
pretty tough
- かなり^よ良かった
quite good

Adjusted Expression

相当^{むづか}難しかったです。

It was considerably difficult.

Example

A 「この^{てすと}テスト、どうだった？」 B 「うん、かなり^{むづか}難しかったよ」

A: How was the test? B: Yeah, it was quite difficult.

Notes

"Kanari" is used to strengthen the degree or impression of something. In this example, B evaluates the test by saying it was "kanari muzukashikatta," meaning quite difficult. Compared with "sugoku," it sounds a little calmer and can be used not only for emotional emphasis but also for a somewhat objective assessment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

degree

assessment

impression

emphasis

sharing a feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

degree expression

assessment expression

impression expression

emphasis

spoken language

Not impossible

なくはない

Naku wa nai

not impossible

Variants

- なくはない
not impossible
- やってみなくはない
I might try it
- 行かなくはない
I could go
- 食べなくはない
I don't exactly dislike it
- できなくはない
I could do it, technically

Adjusted Expression

それをすることも考えられます。

It is possible that I might do it.

Example

A 「いっしょに行く？」 B 「うーん、行かなくはないけど...」

A: Wanna come with me? B: Hmm... I could go, I guess...

Notes

"Naku wa nai" is a double negative that leaves room for a weak affirmation or possibility. In this example, B does not clearly say that they will go, but also does not reject the idea. By saying "ikanaku wa nai kedo...", B leaves open the possibility of going while also showing hesitation or some unstated condition.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

ambiguous affirmation

possibility

implication

hesitation

reserved acceptance

Tags EN

immediate grammar

double negative

ambiguous affirmation

softening emotion

reserved expression

possibility expression

spoken language

Hmm... what should I do?

どうしようかな

Dou shiyou kana

Hmm... what should I do?

Variants

- どうしようかな
Hmm... what should I do?
- どうしよっかな
What should I do...
- どうしたもんかな
I wonder what I should do
- どうしようか
What to do...
- うーん、どうしようかな
Hmm... should I?

Adjusted Expression

どうすればよいか^{かんが}考えています。

I'm considering what to do.

Example

A 「^{えいが}映画、^み見に行く？」 B 「うーん、^いどうしようかな...」

A: Wanna go see a movie? B: Hmm... what should I do?

Notes

"Dou shiyou kana" is used when the speaker cannot decide immediately and begins thinking aloud. In this example, B is neither accepting nor refusing the invitation, but withholds judgment by saying "dou shiyou kana." The sentence-final "kana" gives the utterance a soft, self-directed tone, showing that the speaker is responding to the other person while also beginning an inner dialogue.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

indecision

murmuring

thought initiation

withholding judgment

inner dialogue

Tags EN

immediate grammar

indecision expression

murmuring

thought initiation

withholding judgment

inner dialogue

spoken language

Hmm, I can't decide

うーん、^{まよ}迷うなあ

Uun, mayou naa

Hmm, I can't decide

Variants

- ^{まよ}迷うなあ

Hmm, I can't decide

- ^{まよ}迷うなあ

I'm torn

- うーん、^{まよ}迷うなあ

What should I do?

- どうしようかな

Which one should I pick?

- どっちにしようかな

This is hard to choose

Adjusted Expression

どちらにするか^き決めかねています。

I'm having trouble deciding between the two.

Example

A 「どれにする？」 B 「うーん、^{まよ}迷うなあ。どっちも^よ良さそうだし…」

A: Which one will you pick? B: Hmm, I can't decide. They both seem nice...

Notes

"Uun, mayou naa" is used when the speaker cannot decide right away and lets that indecision come out naturally. In this example, B has not reached a conclusion yet, but shares the hesitation by saying "mayou naa." "Uun" opens the moment of thinking, and "naa" adds a soft, self-directed emotional tone.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

indecision self-talk emotional sharing withholding judgment
hesitation before choosing

Tags EN

immediate grammar indecision expression self-talk emotional sharing
withholding judgment choice spoken language

I wonder if this is okay

これでいいのかな

Kore de ii no kana

I wonder if this is okay

Variants

- これでいいのかな
I wonder if this is okay
- これによかったかな
Was this the right choice?
- こうしてよかったのかな
Was it okay to do it this way?
- これで^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫かな
I wonder if this is all right
- これ^あで合ってるのかな
I wonder if this is correct

Adjusted Expression

これで^{もんだい}問題ないかどうか、^{かくにん}確認しています。

I'm checking to see if this is okay.

Example

A 「^{くれじっと}クレジットで^{はら}払っておいたけど、これでいいのかな」

A: I paid by credit card, but I wonder if this is okay.

Notes

"Kore de ii no kana" is used when the speaker looks back on something they have already done or chosen and wonders whether it was okay. In this example, A has already paid by credit card and feels a little unsure about that choice. The ending "no kana" makes the utterance sound like both a soft question to the listener and a self-directed murmur.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

uncertainty

seeking reassurance

murmur

hesitation after deciding

self-checking

Tags EN

immediate grammar

uncertainty expression

checking expression

inner speech

murmur

self-checking

spoken language

Step by step

いっぽいっぽ
一歩一歩

Ippo ippo

Step by step

Variants

- いっぽいっぽ
一歩一歩

Step by step

- いっぽ
一歩ずつ

One step at a time

- すこ
少しずつ

Bit by bit

- ゆっくりと

Slowly but surely

Adjusted Expression

だんかい お 段階を追って、ちやくじつ すす 着実に進めていきましょう。

Let's move forward steadily, one step at a time.

Example

A 「すぐにはうまくならないけど…」 B 「うん、いっぽいっぽ 一歩一歩、やっぺいこう」

A: I won't get good at it right away... B: Yeah, let's take it step by step.

Notes

"Ippo ippo" expresses the feeling of moving forward little by little without rushing. The repetition creates a tone of encouragement or self-persuasion. It can be used either to encourage someone else or to steady oneself, making it an immediate expression that helps restore resolve in the moment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

progress

effort

perseverance

encouragement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

repetition

encouragement

self-encouragement

spoken language

Much better, at least

ずっとまし

Zutto mashi

Much better / Way better

Variants

- ずっとまし
much better
- まだまし
still better
- こっちの方がましほう
this one's better at least
- ~よりずっとまし
way better than ~

Adjusted Expression

まえ前のものよりは、かなりよ良いです。

It is considerably better than the previous one.

Example

A 「こっちもしっばい失敗したけど」 B 「でも、まえ前よりはずっとましじゃん」

A: This one failed too, though... B: But it's still way better than before.

Notes

"Zutto mashi" is used when something is not fully satisfactory but is still clearly better in comparison. The word "mashi" itself often implies choosing the less bad option among undesirable ones. Adding "zutto" strengthens the sense that the difference is fairly large. It is a spoken expression that finds a small positive point within a negative situation, often with a soft tone of consolation or reluctant approval.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

comparison

compromise

consolation

reluctant approval

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emotion

comparison

relative evaluation

Feeling reluctant / Heavy-hearted

き おも
気が重い

Ki ga omoi

Feeling reluctant / Heavy-hearted

Variants

- なんか気が重い

I feel reluctant

- 正直、気が重い

Honestly, I'm not looking forward to it

- 明日のことを考えると気が重い

Thinking about tomorrow makes me feel heavy-hearted

- 月曜が来ると気が重い

Mondays make me feel reluctant

Adjusted Expression

そのことを考えると、あまり気が進みません。

Thinking about it, I am not very eager to do it.

Example

A 「明日、会議だよな」 B 「そうねえ、正直、気が重い」

A: We have a meeting tomorrow, right? B: Yeah... honestly, I'm not looking forward to it.

Notes

"Ki ga omoi" expresses a psychological burden or reluctance toward something one has to face or would rather avoid. The heaviness is metaphorical, referring not to the body but to the mind. In conversation, it is often accompanied by a sigh or pause, and it works as an immediate expression of the speaker's emotional state in the moment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gloominess

sense of burden

expressing reluctance

Tags EN

immediate grammar

emotion

metaphor

psychological burden

I see that a lot

よく見る^み

Yoku miru

I see that a lot

Variants

- よく見る^み

I see that a lot

- よく見るね^み

You see that a lot

- よく見るやつ^み

That's a common sight

- よく見る光景^{み こうけい}

I keep seeing that

- こういうの、よく見る^み

You see this kind of thing often

Adjusted Expression

頻繁^{ひんぱん}に見かけます^み。

I see it frequently.

Example

A 「こういう写真^{しゃしん}、よく見るよね^み」 B 「うん、たしかに」

A: You see this kind of photo a lot, right? B: Yeah, definitely.

Notes

"Yoku miru" is used to bring up something that the speaker often sees in everyday life and to share that sense of familiarity with the listener. In this example, A says "kou iu shashin, yoku miru yo ne," inviting the listener to recognize the same observation. It is not just a statement of frequency, but an immediate observation that creates a shared sense of "I've seen this kind of thing before."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

observation

sharing

empathy

familiarity

sense of having seen it before

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

observation expression

empathy expression

sharing expression

familiarity

topic making

I hear that a lot

よく^き聞く

Yoku kiku

I hear that a lot

Variants

- よく^き聞く

I hear that a lot

- よく^き聞くね

You hear that a lot

- よく^き聞くやつ

I've heard that before

- よく^き聞く^{はなし}話

That's a common story

- こういう^{はなし}話、よく^き聞く

You hear this kind of thing often

Adjusted Expression

^{ひんぱん}頻繁に^{みみ}耳にします。

I hear it frequently.

Example

A 「こういう^{はなし}話、よく^き聞くよね」 B 「うん、たしかに」

A: You hear this kind of story a lot, right? B: Yeah, definitely.

Notes

"Yoku kiku" is used to bring up a story, phrase, or topic that the speaker often hears and to share that sense of familiarity with the listener. In this example, A says "kou iu hanashi, yoku kiku yo ne," inviting the listener to recognize the same experience or impression. It is not just a statement of frequency, but an immediate observation that creates a shared sense of "I've heard that kind of thing before."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

empathy

observation

sharing

sense of having heard it before

natural reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

observation expression

empathy expression

sharing expression

familiarity from hearing

topic making

More

もっと

Motto

more

Variants

- もっと

more

- もっと^た食べたい

I want more

- もっと^み見せて

Show me more

- もっと^{はや}早く

faster

- もっとちょうだい

Give me more

Adjusted Expression

もう少し^{すこ}追加^{ついか}していただけますか。

Could I have a little more?

Example

A 「もっと^た食べる？」 B 「うん！」

A: Do you want more? B: Yeah!

Notes

"Motto" is used when the speaker wants a greater amount or degree of something. In this example, A asks whether B wants more, and B immediately answers "yeah," showing the desire to eat more. "Motto" can easily function on its own as a request or expression of desire, and it is common in everyday speech. Depending on context, it may refer to more food, greater speed, more repetitions, or a fuller explanation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

addition request increasing degree desire immediate response

Tags EN

immediate grammar adverb request expression desire expression degree expression
immediate response spoken language

I'll be waiting for you

ま
待ってるよ

Matteru yo

I'll be waiting for you

Variants

- ま待ってるよ
I'll be waiting for you
- ま待ってるね
I'll wait for you
- ま待ってるよー
I'll be waiting
- ま待ってるからね
I'll wait, okay?
- さきい先に行って、ま待ってるよ
I'll go ahead and wait for you

Adjusted Expression

ま
お待ちしております。

I will be waiting for you.

Example

A 「先さきに行いってて」 B 「うん、ま待まってるよ」

A: Go ahead without me. B: Sure, I'll be waiting for you.

Notes

"Matteru yo" is used when the speaker tells the listener that they will wait for them. In this example, B says "matteru yo," allowing A to go ahead without feeling rushed. The particle "yo" makes it more than a statement of waiting; it becomes a gentle reassurance directed toward the listener. In formal situations, it is replaced by "o-machi shite orimasu."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reassurance expectation kindness consideration for the listener
stating that one will wait

Tags EN

immediate grammar emotional expression reassurance expression
considerate expression waiting expression spoken language casual speech

I'll do it in advance

...とく

...toku

do something in advance

Variants

- これ、^か買っとく

I'll buy this in advance

- ^{さき}先に^い言っとく

I'll tell you first

- ^{ようい}用意^しとく

I'll prepare it beforehand

- ^お置いとく

I'll leave it there

- ^{おく}送っとく

I'll send it in advance

Adjusted Expression

...ておきます。

I will do it beforehand.

Example

A 「^の飲み^{もの}物、どうする？」 B 「あとで、^か買っとくよ」

A: What about drinks? B: I'll buy them later so we'll have them ready.

Notes

"...toku" is a casual contraction of "...te oku," meaning to do something in advance so that things will be ready later. In this example, B says "kattoku yo," offering to buy the drinks later in preparation. It is not just "buying," but doing it with the later situation in mind. In more formal contexts, the fuller forms "...te okimasu" or "...te okimashou" are used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

preparation

consideration

anticipation

casual offer

planned action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

contracted form

preparation expression

considerate expression

anticipation

auxiliary verb

I should've done it

やっときゃよかった

Yattokya yokatta

I should've done it

Variants

- やっときゃよかった
I should've done it
- 行^いっときゃよかった
I should've gone
- 買^かっときゃよかった
I should've bought it
- 言^いっときゃよかった
I should've said it
- もっと勉強^{べんきょう}しときゃよかった
I should've studied more

Adjusted Expression

やっておけばよかったです。

I should have done it.

Example

A「どうだった？」 B「あと2点^{てんた}足りなかった。もうちょっと勉強^{べんきょう}、やっときゃよかった」

A: How did it go? B: I was short by two points. I should have studied a bit more.

Notes

"Yattokya yokatta" is a casual contraction of "yatte okeba yokatta," expressing regret about something the speaker did not do. In this example, after learning the exam result, B feels that they should have studied more. The form "...toku" comes from "...te oku," meaning to do something in advance. With the conditional "ba" and "yokatta," it becomes an after-the-fact reflection: "I should have done it beforehand."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

regret

not having done something

immediate evaluation

reflection

realization after the fact

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

regret expression

contracted form

reflection

after-the-fact evaluation

auxiliary verb

I'm glad I did it

やっててよかった

Yattete yokatta

I'm glad I did it

Variants

- やっててよかった
I'm glad I did it
- 行っててよかった
I'm glad I went
- 買っててよかった
I'm glad I bought it
- 聞いててよかった
I'm glad I heard it
- 予約しててよかった
I'm glad I made a reservation

Adjusted Expression

やっていてよかったです。

I'm glad I had done it.

Example

A 「事前に予約してた？」 B 「うん、予約しててよかったよ」

A: Did you make a reservation in advance? B: Yeah, I'm glad I did.

Notes

"Yattete yokatta" is a casual contraction of "yatte ite yokatta," used when something the speaker did earlier turns out to have been beneficial. In this example, B evaluates the earlier reservation as a good decision. The form "...tete" comes from the spoken contraction of "...te ite," and it links a past action to present relief or satisfaction.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

satisfaction relief immediate evaluation after-the-fact evaluation

affirming a past action

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language satisfaction expression relief expression

after-the-fact evaluation contracted form auxiliary verb

It's nothing

なんでもない

Nandemo nai

It's nothing

Variants

- なんでもない

It's nothing

- ぜんぜん全然なんでもない

It's totally nothing

- べつ別になんでもない

It's really nothing

- なんでもないよ

Nothing, really

- いや、なんでもない

Never mind

Adjusted Expression

たい大したことではありません。

It's not a big deal.

Example

A 「どうしたの？」 B 「なんでもない」

A: What's wrong? B: It's nothing.

Notes

"Nandemo nai" is used when the speaker wants to say that nothing is wrong, or when they want to take back something they started to say. In this example, B says "nandemo nai" to indicate that there is no problem. However, it can be used not only when nothing is really wrong, but also when the speaker does not want to worry the listener, wants to hide their feelings, or wants to retract a half-spoken thought. A soft tone can reassure the listener, while a stronger tone can sound dismissive.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

denial

reassurance

evasion

retraction

holding back emotion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

denial expression

reassurance expression

evasive expression

retraction expression

emotion

Got a moment now?

^{いま}
今、ちょっと、いい？

Ima, chotto, ii?

Got a moment now?

Variants

- 今、ちょっといい？
Do you have a moment now?
- 今、ちょっといいですか
Is now a good time?
- 今、いい？
Got a sec?
- 今、少し、いい？
Can I talk to you for a second?

Adjusted Expression

^{いま}
今、少し、よろしいですか。

Do you have a moment now?

Example

A 「^{いま}今、ちょっと、いい？」 B 「うん、どうしたの？」

A: Got a moment now? B: Yeah, what's up?

Notes

"Ima, chotto, ii?" is used when the speaker wants to start a conversation while checking whether the other person is available. Here, "chotto" does not simply mean "a little" in a literal sense. It also softens the approach and makes the request less direct. The final "ii?" is elliptical, and a form like "Ima, chotto, ii desu ka" sounds a little more polite. In everyday conversation, brief pauses between the words help create a natural opening and give the listener room to respond.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

attention call

consideration

conversation start

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

consideration

attention call

conversation start

Since we're at it

どうせなら

Douse nara

since we're at it

Variants

- どうせなら
since we're at it
- どうせなら行こう
since we're at it, let's go
- どうせならやってみよう
we might as well try
- どうせなら言えればいい
you might as well say it
- どうせなら、泊まっていこう
since we're already here, let's stay over

Adjusted Expression

せっかくですから、そのようにしましょう。

Since we have the opportunity, let's do that.

Example

A 「もう遅いよ」 B 「どうせなら、泊まっていこうよ」

A: It's already late. B: Since we're at it, we might as well stay over.

Notes

"Douse nara" is used when the speaker takes the current situation as a starting point and suggests a better or more practical next move. In this example, B responds to the fact that it is already late and suggests staying over. "Douse" sets up the sense that the situation is already this way, and "nara" leads from that condition to the next action. It is an immediate judgment expression that can turn a somewhat negative situation into a more positive choice.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

suggestion

immediate judgment

change of direction

positive choice

making use of the situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

suggestion expression

judgment expression

change of direction

making use of the situation

casual speech

See?

ほらね

Hora ne

See?

Variants

- ほらね
See?
- ほらね!
See!
- ほらね、言ったでしょ
See, I told you
- ほらね、だから言ったんだ
See, that's why I said it
- ほら、やっぱり
See, just as expected

Adjusted Expression

わたし い とお
私が言った通りでしょう。

It is just as I said.

Example

A 「やっぱりあめふ雨が降ってきたね」 B 「ほらね」

A: It started raining after all. B: See?

Notes

"Hora ne" is used when the speaker's prediction or earlier statement turns out to be true and they point this out to the listener. In this example, the prediction that it would rain has come true, and B responds briefly with "hora ne." Said gently, it can sound like shared confirmation, but said strongly, it can sound like "I told you so." Although short, it is an immediate confirmation expression whose tone can convey either closeness or self-assertion.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation confirming a prediction shared feeling self-assertion
addressing the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language confirmation expression confirming a prediction
empathy expression self-assertion casual speech

Likewise

こちらこそ

Kochira koso

Likewise

Variants

- こちらこそ
Likewise
- こちらこそ、ありがとう
No, thank you
- こちらこそ、すみません
No, I'm the one who should apologize
- こちらこそ、よろしく
Likewise, nice to meet you
- いえいえ、こちらこそ
No, the feeling is mutual

Adjusted Expression

わたし ほう私の方こそ、もう あそう申し上げるべきです。

It is I who should say that.

Example

A 「ありがとう！」 B 「こちらこそ、ありがとう」

A: Thank you! B: No, thank you.

Notes

"Kochira koso" is used to return the other person's thanks, apology, or greeting from the speaker's side. In this example, B responds to A's "thank you" with "kochirakoso, arigatou," making the gratitude mutual rather than one-directional. The particle "koso" adds the sense that it is really the speaker who should be saying it. It is an immediate response expression that softly returns thanks, apology, or greeting and helps adjust the relationship.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

response

modesty

reciprocity

relationship adjustment

returning thanks or apology

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

response expression

modesty expression

reciprocity

response to thanks

response to apology

With all your might

おも
思いっきり

Omoikkiri

with all your might

Variants

- ^{おも}思いっきり^{はし}走る
run with all your might
- ^{おも}思いっきり^{わら}笑う
laugh out loud
- ^{おも}思いっきり^{おこ}怒る
get really angry
- ^{おも}思いっきり^{たの}楽しむ
enjoy it to the fullest
- ^{おも}思いっきり^な投げる
throw it with all your might

Adjusted Expression

^{ちから}力いっぱい、やってください。

Please do it with full force.

Example

A 「どうやって^な投げるの？」 B 「思いっきり^{おも}投^なげて！」

A: How should I throw it? B: Throw it with all your might!

Notes

"Omoikkiri" expresses doing something without holding back one's force or emotion. In this example, B says "omoikkiri nagete," telling A to throw it strongly without restraint. It is used not only for physical force, but also for emotional release, as in "laugh with all your heart" or "enjoy it to the fullest." Depending on the situation, it can express positive release or strong anger and scolding.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis

emotion

full force

momentum

release

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

emphasis expression

emotional expression

full-force expression

adverb

casual speech

The moment

とたん

Totan

the moment

Variants

- ^た立ったとたん
the moment I stood up
- ^い言ったとたん
the moment I said it
- ^で出かけたとたん
the moment I left
- ^{そと}^で外に出たとたん
the moment I stepped outside
- ^つ着いたとたん
the moment I arrived

Adjusted Expression

...した^{ちよくご}直後に、...

immediately after ... happened, ...

Example

A 「外^{そと}に出^でたとたん、雨^{あめ}が降^ふり出^だしたよ」 B 「うわ、^た^い^み^ん^ぐ^わ^るタイミング悪いね」

A: The moment I stepped outside, it started raining. B: Wow, bad timing.

Notes

"Totan" is used to show that one event happened immediately after another. In this example, it started raining right after A stepped outside. "Totan" does not simply show chronological order; it gives the sense that the second event occurred suddenly, triggered by or closely tied to the first. For this reason, it is often used for unexpected changes or unfortunate timing.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

immediacy

temporal connection

change

unexpected occurrence

event chain

Tags EN

immediate grammar

linking expression

time expression

event chain

unexpected occurrence

spoken language

written language

Unexpectedly

おも
思いがけず

Omoigakezu

unexpectedly

Variants

- おも 思いがけず^あ会った
I met someone unexpectedly
- おも 思いがけず^{たす}助かった
I was unexpectedly helped
- おも 思いがけず^ほ褒められた
I was unexpectedly praised
- おも 思いがけず^み見つかった
I found it unexpectedly
- おも 思いがけずうまくいった
It unexpectedly went well

Adjusted Expression

よそうがい
予想外に

unexpectedly

Example

A 「おも 思いがけず、えき 駅でせんせい 先生に あ 会ったよ」 B 「へえ、そんなところで？」

A: Unexpectedly, I ran into my teacher at the station. B: Oh, in a place like that?

Notes

"Omoigakezu" is used when something happens that the speaker did not expect. In this example, A did not expect to meet their teacher at the station, so they use "omoigakezu." It can be used for both positive and troublesome events, but in either case it gives the sense that the event came from outside the speaker's plan or expectation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

unexpectedness coincidence surprise unforeseen development receiving an event

Tags EN

immediate grammar adverb unexpected event unexpectedness coincidence
event description spoken language

Shall I...?

しょうか

Shiyou ka

Shall I...?

Variants

- ^{てっだ}手伝おうか

Shall I help?

- ^も持ってこようか

Shall I bring it?

- ^あ開けようか

Shall I open it?

- ^も持とうか

Shall I carry it?

- ^よ呼ぼうか

Shall I call someone?

Adjusted Expression

^{てっだ}お手伝いいたしましょうか。

Would you like me to help?

Example

A 「^{にもつ}荷物、^{おも}重そうだね。^も持とうか？」 B 「^{たす}ありがとう、助かる」

A: Your bag looks heavy. Shall I carry it? B: Thanks, that would help.

Notes

"Shiyou ka" is used here when the speaker offers to do something for the listener. In this example, A sees that the listener's bag looks heavy and says "motou ka," offering to carry it. The expression can also be used for inviting someone to do something together, as in "ikou ka," but forms like "tetsudaou ka," "motou ka," and "akeyou ka" often function as offers in which the speaker acts for the listener. In formal situations, expressions such as "o-tetsudai itashimashou ka" or "o-mochi shimashou ka" are used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

offer

consideration

thoughtfulness

helping

reducing the listener's burden

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

offer expression

consideration expression

thoughtfulness

helping expression

casual speech

Colophon

Title	An Expression A Day
Author	Hilofumi Yamamoto, Ph.D.
Range	No. 401-500 / 99 entries
License	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)
Source	Generated from AEAD JSON data.